

<p style="text-align: center;">The Problems in Researching Homogenized Sentences</p>		Linguistics
		<p>Keywords: homogeneous sentences, turcology, generalizer unit, derivative, auxiliary, component.</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>The opinions of scholars about the homogenized sentences, its essence, structure and giving it in texts in the Uzbek linguistics are given in this article. To give homogenizer and generalizer units in the compound of homogenized sentence, to form homogeneous chain parts grammatically are studied more by Uzbek scientists and linguists.</p>		

The homogenizer, generalizer units and some subjects must have in the compound of homogenized sentences. The person who makes every action must be specified separately; otherwise it will be another device, not homogenized sentence. When we talk about the homogeneous phenomenon, of course, it is important that the issue of homogenizer unit must be in first place. In order to the parts of the speeches to come to be homogenized, of course, it must be a homogenizer unit. R. Sayfullaeva said that this homogenizer unit was used in the compound of the parts of the sentences, and that it could be in three types:

- 1) *in the form of an annex;*
- 2) *in one word form;*
- 3) *in many word forms: bo'larekan, bo'lar emish*

Parts that constitute the homogeneous chain can be form grammatically different:

- a) The homogenizer unit may be added to each section;
- b) The homogenizer unit may be added to the last part. This feature has been widely studied by Turcologic scholars and Uzbek linguists.

Grammatical formations of the parts of homogeneous, in any cases, should be regarded as integral to them. This phenomenon is particularly evident when it comes after the last part of the homogenizer unit, and it is important to give the opinion of Kononov:

“The morphological element can be attached only to the last member, when the enumerated members seem to merge into one complex member of the sentence”.

A.G'ulomov and, in general, Uzbek linguists support the opinion of A.N.Kononov. The combination of the last part of the homogenizer unit is mainly the methodological feature of the Uzbek language. This phenomenon also comes from the point of view of a syntactic economy and does not allow repetition.

The combination of homogenizer unit to the last part does not depend on the above mentioned phenomenon. Using of the homogenizer unit may change the essence of some of the phenomenon.

For example, in the sample *u yozayotgan, ukase televizor ko'rayotgan edi, edi* homogenizer unit adds to the next part, and it homogenizes two parts. If we use this unit after each section, as well as we have two independent statements.

U yozayotgan edi.

Ukasi televizor ko'rayotgan edi – we have two independent statements. *Aholisi ham, maydoni ham, Moskvadan, Leningraddan<Kiyevdan keyin to'rtinchi o'rinda turar ekan.*

Usually, a homogeneous is a combination of some kind of unity around something. But that homogenizer unit is not always used. In the above example, *-dan* is general for three units and homogenized them with each other. The units *Aholisi ham, maydoni ham* have all characters which are specific to homogenous part, so they are considered a homogenous part (in this case).

Although these units do not have a homogenizer unit, we explain them as homogenous subjects. And it should be noted that homogenized units such as *hammasi, harjihati* can be used.

Then, when we think about the phenomenon of the homogenous, we must say that it is not the same as the whole of the parts of the sentences (unity, the homogenizer unit), and that this is a natural phenomenon. When studying phenomenon of homogenous at the units chapter, considering it given on the basis of simple sentence [ABKk], it should be understood that homogenizing verb and units around it are different phenomenon (radically different phenomenon). This issue requires a thorough and broad studying. Homogenizing parts of the sentences can be given the following models:

[$\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \Theta_3, \Theta_4 + \Theta_n +$ homogenizer unit R[ABKk];

[$T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4 + T_n +$ homogenizer unit R[ABKk];

[$A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4 + A +$ homogenizer unit R [ABKk];

[$X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 + X +$ homogenizer unit R [ABKk]

[{(AB₁, R AB₂)} Kk]

These models can be shown that homogenous phenomenon will be different from one glance. The same approach cannot be used to analyze this phenomenon in the sample of different derivatives. We think that the issue of difference between homogenizing of the parts of the speech in Uzbek language and in other languages and the derivative are studied on the basis of

characters of Russian language and the other problems will be special research theme. That is why we did not stop them separately.

The issue of homogenous is a very well-studied topic of Turcology, including Uzbek language. In this regard Kononov AN, Zakiev M.Z., Balakaev I.B., Dmitriev N.V., Gulomov A.G. Ubaeva U., Boltaboeva X., D. Mukhamedova's researches have been discussed.

In her research, D.Muhamedova considers the auxiliaries as a generalizer unit, and writes: "The nouns or words which come with nouns join together with the most recent component of the homogenous sentences, it is general for all, and she gives the following example:

“Mariya Vasilyevnaning kabinetini turli navgʻoʻza tuplari, xosildorlik diagrammalari, iqtisodiy jadvallar bilan bezatilgan edi.

In our opinion, the derivatives, convergence suffixes + derivative are not the generalizer unit, but they are general in some parts. One of the examples we have cited is the following: *Qodirning ishi, Musharraf fojeasi, turgan shaharlarning obod boʻlishi, ob-havo, narx-navo hammasi haqida gaplashdilar (Shuhrat).*

Qodirning ishi – Musharraf fojeasi + turgan shaharlarning obod boʻlishi – ob-havo – narx-navo – hammasi haqida. In this example, it is taken out of the "brackets" and is called “обобщающая грамматическая форма” – "generalized grammatical form".

It is natural phenomenon for derivatives to use individually when using them individually. It is necessary to use them separately, but not with separate words, and, when necessary, out of the "brackets" with the word that comes before it. In this example, if we use both the words *hammasi* and *haqida* separately, the content of the sentence will be ruined:

Qodirning ishi, Musharraf fojeasi, turgan shaharlarning obod boʻlishi, ob-havo, narx-navo – hammasi gaplashdilar?

Qodirning ishi, Musharraf fojeasi, turgan shaharlarning obod boʻlishi, ob-havo, narx-navo – haqida gaplashdilar?

As you can see from the examples, it is impossible to use separately the words *haqida* and *hammasi*. If necessary, take them out of the brackets. The author writes that the derivatives come in the compound of verb part of the group of derivatives, the generalizing unit of the collective writes the following: "... uchun the conjunction of the type and the relative words can come from the functions of the verb and execute its function.

For example, the words such as *bu oila chiqish, turar-joy sharoitini yaxshilash, “Sen tinch-koʻshning tinch” iborasining hayotiy bir haqiqat ekanligini isbotlash uchun* (“Mushtum”)

“*boqish*”, “*isbotlash*” are used with *uchun* auxiliary, and it serves as the verb. The same opinions were expressed that the auxiliary “*haqida*”, “*to’g’risida*”, the words “*kerak*”, “*mumkin*” were used in the compound of [Kk].

D.Muhamedova pointed out that it was possible to meet the grammatical signs in homogenized sentences such as the homogenous parts, they are *edi*, *-di*, *-deb*. This issue is studied more detailed in the work of R. Sayfullaeva. The author also write that the units which are used out of the brackets, divide into three groups, as we mention above.

- 1) as the form addition to the word;
- 2) in a word form;
- 3) many words form.

Usually this supplementary is added to the last word which serves as the verb form, and it serves to form the other parts that are used within that device.

For example: *Uning qulog’iga na bulbulning ovozi kirardi, na ko’ziga uyqu kelardi* (P.Tursun). *Soy g’uvillab oqar va uning muzdek shamoli qirg’oqda tartibsiz o’sgan o’tlarni silkitardi*. (S.Nazar). The supplementary *-di* has already been added to last verb in both sentences. This supplementary belongs to the verbs of the first part *-kirardi ...-oqardi*. The – *kirar* verb of the first part of the first sentence *Uning qulog’iga na bulbulning ovozi kirardi, na ko’ziga uyqu kelardi* is not formed by the grammatical form, the supplementary which forms the verb of the second part, belongs to the verb of the first sentence (*kirardi*). *Ovozi* in the first part of the sentence is subject, *uyquin* the second part is subject, if the supplementary *-di* is added to each part, this homogenized sentence will be the composite sentence:

Uning qulog’iga na bulbulning ovozi kirardi.
Na ko’ziga uyqu kelardi.

-di is added to the last verb from the point of view of syntactic economics and style. The two verbs in this part of the sentence have the same verb indicators:

In the first part and the second part of the second example, there is also a subject (*soy* – subject: *shamoli* - subject). The verb of the last part is added the supplementary *-di*, it belongs to the verb of the first part. The verb of the first part is [AB] = *oq*, *- ar* the one part of [Kk], the second part [AB] = *silkitga* are the same for each of them, *-di* is the general for each f them. As we can see, in our examples, the components of [Kk] are the same.

There are many examples in Uzbek language that the verb has been formed with different verb indicators. In the first parts of our research, we had just dropped off on the verb indicators. Although the verb indicators are different in the parts of the sentence, only one unit in the compound of them may be the same.

For example, Масалан, *Lekin hayajondan barmoqlarim chanoqlarga to'g'ri bormasdi, chanoq uchlari tirnoqlarim orasiga kirib kelardi.* (N.Kobul). This sentence consists of two parts, the verb of the first part – *to'g'ri bormas* is formed fully by the grammatical form; The verb of the second part – *kirib kelardi* – is formed fully by the grammatical form. The compound of the verb of the first part consists of the followings: [AB] – *to'g'ri bor*, [Kk] – *-mas*. The compound of the verb of the second part consists of the followings: [AB] – *kiribkel*, [Kk] – *ar + -di*.

A unit of [Kk] in compound of the second part verb form fully the verb *-di* by grammatically, and it also belongs to the first part of the verb and can serve to formulate it in grammatical form: *Lekin hayajondan barmoqlarim chanoqlarga to'g'ri bormasdi* In this case, the given sentence will be fully composite sentence and it will be the typical form of [ABKk, ABKk]. *Lekin hayajondan barmoqlarim chanoqlarga to'g'ri bormasdi, chanoq uchlari tirnoqlarim orasiga kirib kelardi.* – [ABKk, ABKk] It is possible to use these two parts separately. Each of them has features specific to simple sentences. [ABKk, ABKk] – [ABKk], [ABKk]. In these sentences the compound of [Kk] can be different and can be general in a single unit of its compound (in examples, the supplementary *-di*). Our actual materials are shown that the other units which come before the general unit, may be the same and often different. We will record the following types of elements that come before the general unit in the compound [Kk]:

1) *gan* in the first part of the compound of [Kk] and *-a* in the second part of the compound of [Kk], for instance: *Biriyig'ibo'lgan, biriyebo'ladi.* /Oybek/

The supplementary *-di* is used in the second part of this sample, it forms the verb of the first part grammatically: *Bir iyig'i bo'lgandi* – [AB] = *yig'i bo'l*, [Kk] = *-gan + di.* *Biriyebo'ladi.* [AB] = *yebo'l*, [Kk] = *-a + -di.*

2) *-gan* in the first part of the compound and *-mas* in the second part of the compound of [Kk]: *Hamma bir-biridan yaxshi kiyingan, lekin hech kimning kiyimi birovnikiga o'xshamasdi.* (P.Tursun).

[AB] = *yaxshikiyin* – [Kk] = *-gan*;
[AB] = *o'xsha* – [Kk] = *-mas + -di.*

3) *-mas* in the first part of the compound of қисм[Kk] and *-ar* in the second part of the compound of [Kk]:

Lekin oyim buni tushuntirgisi kelmas, u bulturdan beri uni qiynab kelardi. (O.Yokubov).

[AB] = *kel* -, [KK] = - *mas*;
 [AB] = *qiynabkel* -, [KK] = - *ar* + - *di*

4) - *ar* in the first part of the compound of [KK], - *mas* in the second part of the compound of [KK]: *Bu odam hamma vaqt xursand yurar, yuzidan tabassum arimasdi (P.Tursun).*

[AB] = *xursandyur* -, [KK] = - *ar*

[AB] = *ari* -, [KK] = - *mas* + - *di*.

Ko'p bolalar undan qo'rqar, Xolmurod qo'rqmasdi. (P.Tursun).

[AB] = *qo'rq-*, [KK] = - *ar*

[AB] = *qo'rq-*, [KK] = -*mas* + - *di*.

5) *-magan* in the first part of the compound of [KK], -*ar* in the second part of the compound of [KK]:

...unga bu haqda gapirib o'tirishga hojat qolmagan, chunki u ham menga ishonardi (O. Yokubov).

[AB] *qol* -, [KK] = - *ma* + - *gan*

[AB] *ishon* -, [KK] = *ar* + - *di*.

6) -*dir* + -*gan* in the first part of the compound of [KK], - *y* - + - *di* in the second part of the compound of [KK].

Childiroqlarning mayin musiqasi hamma yoqni to'ldirgan, go'yo kechaning o'zi kuylaydi. (Oybek).

[AB] = *to'l* -, [KK] = - *dir* - + - *gan*,

[AB] = *kuyla* -, [KK] = - + - *di*.

7) -*gan* in the first part of the compound of [KK], -*y* -, + - *di* in the second part of the compound of [KK].

Qorong'i tushib qolgan, surma rang osmonda birin-ketin chiroq yoqilgandek yulduzlar miltillaydi. (S. Zunnunova).

[AB] = *tushibqol* -, [KK] = - *gan*,

[AB] = *miltilla* -, [KK] = - *y* - + - *di* and others.

Examples can be continued. We have just given the most common forms. Sometimes the first part can be used as [Kk] – b, the second part [Kk] – ar forms, and generalized with the supplementary –*di*.

Yaqin yonveridan otlarning pishqirgani, aravalar g'ijir-g'ijiri, avtomobillar gumbur-gumburi ko'tarilib, odamlarning xayqirig'i eshitilib qolardi. /X. Nazir/.

It is expedient that the supplementary *-di* could be included in the verb of the first part of these sentences:

- | | | |
|----|--|------------------------------------|
| 1. | | <i>pishqirgani</i> |
| 2. | | <i>g'ijir-g'ijiri ko'tarilibdi</i> |
| 3. | | <i>gumbur-gumburi</i> |

In this case, the device should not be added to the compound of homogenous sentence, it should be added to the compound of composite sentence. It is interesting that the supplementary *-di* is often used in the compound of the last verb. In some cases, the another part may be used between the grammatically shaped part with the first part, for example, ... *bu uy bundan o'n ikki-o'n uch yil oldin qanday turgan bo'lsa, shunday turar, u mahallarda bu azim terak ancha yosh edi, endi bo'lsa, belidan pastrog'idagi bir ikki shoxlari qurib qolibdi./ O.Yokubov/.*

The supplementary *-di* homonizes the following parts:

a / ... bu uya bundan o'n ikki-o'n uch yil oldin qanday turgan bo'lsa, shunday turar.

This part is the composite sentence, $[ABKk \rightarrow ABKk]$, the verb of its next part is not formed $[AB] = \text{tur -}$, $[Kk] = \text{- ar}$;

b/ endi bo'lsa, belidan pastrog'idagi bir ikki shoxlari qurib qolibdi.

$[AB] = \text{quribqol -}$, $(Kk) = \text{- ib + - di}$.

The supplementary *-di* has not the parts which create simple sentences, but it belongs to parts which create composite sentences.

The part "*bu azim terak ancha yosh edi*" is used only between the two parts, but its verb is grammatically fully formed $[AB] = [Kk] = \text{.edi}$.

Most of the expressions we use in our mother tongue are divided into three parts. Although the formation of the verb components is almost identical in these words, the subject is definitely used, namely, the writers are trying to use the synonym (s) of the words that are in the possession of the subject, and thus, intentionally to increase the power of influence by means of affirmation.

In the example, supplementary *-dir* is compound of the verb of the second part, and it also belongs to verb of the first part. The supplementary *-dir* is used out of the bracket, because of its potential. The components of the verbs of the first and second parts are as follows:

[AB] = bo'l -, [Kk] = - gan,
[AB] = uchibyor -, [Kk] = - gan + - dir.

When *-dir* is used in the compound of homogenized sentences, the compound of [AB] is different, we explain some of them:

a) *Bu favqulodda navozish sababini o'ylamoqqa xojining vaqti yo'q, chunki o'zining qayg'usi, o'ylashga, fikrlashga yetarlidir. /A.Kadiri/.* In this sample, the first part [AB] = *yo'q*, [Kk] = - Ø -.

The second part [AB] = *yetarlik*, [Kk] = - *dir* this supplementary *-dir* is absent. It belongs to [AB]:

- 1) *Bu favqulodda navozish sababini o'ylamoqqa xojining vaqti yo'qdir.*
- 2) *O'zning qayg'usi, o'ylashga, fikrlashga yetarlidir.*
- 3) *Hamma ish joyida, lekin bir narsagina ko'ngilning ingichka yerini jarohatlaydir.*

The first part in the device [AB] is represented by the word “*joyida*”, and [Kk] is equal to Ø -. The second part [AB] is expressed by “*jarohatla*”, and [KK] is equal to ã + *-dir*.

-dir can easily be added to the compound of the first part of [AB], so this device is not homogenized sentence. It is one of the typical types of composite sentence [ABKk, Kk].

b / *Men bilaman iqbol bizniki,*
Biznikidir saodat sharaf /Uygun/.

In this example, the following two parts are homogenized, they are used in the compound of complex portable sentence. The first part is a generalized sentence and the *-dir* supplementary is not related to it, but it serves to form the verb of the second part: *iqbol biznikidir*. In this case, it is possible to distinguish this device to separate sentences:

Men bilaman.
Iqbol biznikidir.
Biznikidir saodat – sharaf.

It should be said that it does not always use –dir supplementary in out of the bracket, if it is used as the personality meaning, it has not opportunity to use it in out of the bracket, for example,

Qutidor eshik oldida qo'l qovushtirib mehmonlarni kutib oladir, yer ostidan kuyoviga ko'z qirini tashlab, kishiga sezdirmay o'zicha kulimsirab qo'yadir / A. Kadiri/.... *faqat jongina suraydir, majruh ko'klarga ukki na otadir* /A. Kadiri/.

Ko'rinishda uning kuli, amm haqiqatda Otabekning ma'naviy padari bo'lgan Hasanali ota uning maxfiy dardining asli omilini izlaydilar, bekning o'zi bo'lsa, o'z holi to'g'risida hech narsa sezdirmay, dardini yashiradir/A.Kadiri/.

In the first and second examples, *-dir* supplementary gives the meaning of personality, also its one part is in the compound of the verb, it creates [ABKk, ABKk] typical type of the composite sentence, it can be used that some part of –dir supplementary can be debased and used out of the bracket.

The third example, *-kuli*, *-dir* supplementary can be added to the part of the first part verb. This device has not –dir which has characters of generalization. The first part [AB] is equal to *kuliga*, [Kk] - Ø. The second part is [AB] = *izlay* - [Kk] = *-dir*, the third part [AB] = *- yashir*, [Kk] - a + *-dir*.

If –dir the verb indicator is used as a verb indicator or supplementary of personality, it will generate homogenous sentences. In general, *-dir* which is one unit of the [Kk] component, may have previously been added to a few other [AB] units. The issue of the components of [Kk], namely, the issue category of the verb, is not studied in Uzbek language.

We focused on two supplementary which the most commonly used “out of the brackets”. Generally speaking, the rule which used some supplementary out of the bracket, is closely related to the structural problem of the category of the verb.

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